

Discovery of diverse small RNAs from buffalo milk transcriptome by data mining approach

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ABSTRACT

The present study is a first attempt to discover different types of RNAs from milk somatic cells of lactating buffaloes. Lactation is an intricate process regulated by several molecular RNA drivers. In order to improve milk production it is necessary to identify and understand the molecular factors that regulate lactation. Techniques of data mining are used to find hidden patterns and information within data sets. The RNA discovery was accomplished by mining of RNA sequencing data of 12 samples of somatic cells derived from buffalo milk at different stages of lactation. The processed reads were aligned to the human reference genome with a mapping percentage ranging from 85.87 to 99.70. The aligned data was annotated using reference databases such as miRBase, piRNABank, piRBase, piRNA Cluster, circBase, GENCODE and gtrNAdb. Maximum numbers of circRNAs were identified in our dataset followed by piRNAs and then miRNAs. We were able to elucidate several distinct miRNAs, piRNAs, snRNAs, snoRNAs, circRNAs and tRNA in buffalo milk somatic cells. A comprehensive understanding of the RNA regulators of lactation will help in improving and managing milk production in buffaloes. Our study is also a step towards complete annotation of the buffalo genome.

Keywords-Next Generation Sequencing, RNAseq, Data mining, RNA

I. INTRODUCTION

In modern day era, Next Generation Sequencing (NGS) technology offers high performance, scalability and throughput with ultra-high speed and efficiency for determining a nucleotide sequence in an entire genome or specific regions of DNA or RNA [1]. Complex genomics questions today demand a high level of information beyond what can be acquired from traditional DNA sequencing methods. NGS has filled that gap and has become a handy tool to address these questions [2]. Having knowledge of the genome's functional elements is essential to

understanding the genome. It is the transcriptome, a set of various types of RNA, like microRNA (miRNA) [3], P-element-induced wimpy testis (PIWI) interacting RNAs (piRNA) [4], transfer RNAs (tRNA) [5], small nuclear RNAs (snRNA) [6], small nucleolar RNAs (snoRNA) [7], circular RNAs (circRNA) and some non-coding sequences, that determine the function of the genome. A large number of research projects focus on the analysis of the transcriptome instead of the entire genome because 80-90% of the transcribed genes do not form proteins. However, they play an important role in gene expression regulation. Additionally, non coding RNAs that are not translated to proteins play critical roles. For example, snoRNAs regulate rRNA splicing, snRNAs participate in mRNA splicing, tRNA plays an important role in translation, miRNA is involved in translational repression, piRNAs control gene expression during transcription and post-transcriptional processes, while circRNA plays an important role in gene regulation expression and biological development. In deciphering the information about all these RNAs, data mining techniques play an important role. With the rapid growth of NGS applications, new methods of data storage, analysis, and visualization are required. Techniques from statistics and artificial intelligence, including machine learning [8] and neural networks [9] are used for mining the NGS data. The use of NGS has generated a plethora of genetic and transcriptomic data. Through these datasets, data mining can be used to identify patterns, correlations and knowledge. Data mining is a term that refers to obtaining knowledge from large amounts of data by digging or "mining". Enhancing the communication between data mining techniques and NGS data has great potential to detect and characterize the core components of RNA which are critical in NGS based RNA analysis. Therefore, the present study aimed to discover different types of RNAs from RNA sequencing data of milk somatic cells of lactating

buffaloes. Since lactation is a complex process regulated by several molecular RNA drivers, it is necessary to identify and understand the molecular factors that regulate this process. A comprehensive understanding of the RNA regulators of lactation will help in improving and managing milk production in buffaloes.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

- 1) *RNAseq data source*: The Sequence Read Archive (SRA) at NCBI is the main repository for next-generation sequencing data. This work adopted a real data set which was downloaded from the GenBank with accession number GGR000000001, under BioProject PRJNA453843. The data set contains 12 fastq files of buffalo milk somatic cells from early, mid and late lactation phase [10].
- 2) *Pre-processing of RNAseq data*: As a result of the experimental and sequencing procedures, raw read data often contain biases and complex artifacts. These interfere strongly with accurate read alignments, influencing the results of subsequent analyses. To increase downstream analysis, accuracy and reduce computational requirements (RAM, disk space, and execution time), it is best to preprocess raw read data. For generating this quality statistics of the raw reads FastQC tool was used. The results of FastQC [11] provide information of number of reads, GC content, quality of samples, presence or absence of adapters, over-represented sequences, average length of the sequences, sequence duplication level etc. On the basis of FastQC generated report, the sequences of low quality were removed. A quality threshold of 30 (Q30) was used and data having a score \geq Q30 was further analyzed. CUTADAPT [12] tool was used for trimming of reads. The output of the CUTADAPT was again used for quality check with FastQC tool to ensure the accuracy of the samples for further processing. STAR aligner [14] was used to accurately align the processed reads to the human reference genome (GRCh38.p13-GCA_000001405.28).

- 3) *Mining of diverse RNAs*: The different kinds of RNAs were mined using specific databases available. miRBase [14] was used for mining miRNA; piRNABank [16], piRBase [17] and piRNA Cluster [18] for piRNA; gtRNAdb [19] for tRNA; GENCODE [20] for snRNA and snoRNA, while circBase [13] was used for discovery of circular RNA. The input mapped data was annotated against these databases for pattern evaluation of miRNAs, piRNAs, tRNAs, snRNAs, snoRNAs and circRNAs as mined data. The annotation was done using COMPSRA (COMprehensive Platform for Small RNA Analysis) pipeline [21].

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

The raw reads for all samples had a read length ranging from 1 to 101nt. In this paper major focus was on mining of miRNA, piRNA, tRNA, snRNA, snoRNA and circRNA. Since all of these RNAs are of length greater than 15nt, all reads having a length lesser than 15nt were removed. Over-represented sequences also need to be removed from the dataset; however it was observed that there were no over-represented sequences in our data. Each sample had an average of more than 47 million raw reads. More than 45 million reads were obtained for each sample after trimming and filtering. Approximately 32 million reads were trimmed for reasons such as poor quality, adapter content or short length (Table 1).

Table 1. Distribution of raw reads v/s processed reads across different stages of lactation in buffalo milk transcriptome.

Stages	Sample name	Raw reads	Processed reads
Early	B1	98060582	95813942
	B2	73845150	71342054
	B3	63252478	61742742
	B4	47773688	45934730
Mid	B5	88926132	85783112
	B6	86709746	82933892
	B7	80978704	77625076
	B8	105728098	102027752
Late	B9	108754608	104701682
	B10	48109684	46886432
	B11	114278262	110975854
	B12	69643178	67927406

Human reference genome (GRCh38.p13-GCA_000001405.28) was chosen for alignment of the reads as it is better annotated than buffalo genome. The mapping percentage of the samples with respect to the reference genome is given in Fig. 1. It was observed that all the samples aligned to the reference genome with a high mapping percent ranging from 85.87 to 99.70.

Fig 1. Alignment of processed reads of milk somatic cells with Human reference genome.

The mapped reads were further evaluated against the different databases like miRBase, piRNA Bank, piRBase, piRNA Cluster, gtRNAdb, GENCODE and circBase for mining different types of RNAs (Fig. 2). A total of 823708 circRNA; 673 miRNA; 3052 piRNA; 106 snoRNA; 513 snRNA and 199 tRNA were extracted from the RNAseq data. The average number of circRNA, miRNA, piRNA, snoRNA, snRNA and tRNA discovered was 68642, 56, 254, 8, 42 and 16 respectively (Table 2). Maximum numbers of circRNAs were identified in our dataset followed by piRNAs and then miRNAs.

Fig. 2 Distribution of mined RNAs across all the samples of buffalo milk somatic cells

Table 2. Summary of different RNAs mined from buffalo milk somatic cell samples

Sample	circRNA	miRNA	piRNA	snoRNA	snRNA	tRNA
B1	68821	65	274	13	49	21
B2	65912	60	240	8	33	22
B3	58158	40	240	10	34	7
B4	60428	36	262	2	41	0
B5	68036	52	257	7	52	16
B6	74102	61	239	13	48	14
B7	73127	44	226	9	46	18
B8	77059	61	260	14	50	27
B9	74988	66	256	11	42	18
B10	57655	66	209	2	33	0
B11	74826	67	272	9	49	36
B12	70596	55	317	8	36	20

Distribution of small RNAs across different stages of lactation in buffalo revealed that highest number of circRNA, snoRNA, snRNA and tRNA were present in mid stage, while miRNA and piRNA were abundant in late stage of lactation. Several studies have also identified different types of RNA in plants as well as animal species. Highest number of circRNA was also identified in human serum samples [21] while 1182 miRNA were detected in human milk samples [22]. A total of 249 miRNAs were identified in bovine milk somatic cells [23] and about 400 unique miRNAs were detected in cattle milk infected with mastitis [24].

Our results also reflect the availability or annotation of different RNAs in the human genome. The discovery of more RNA molecules of different types in other livestock species will further replenish the databases. This study elucidated distinct RNA molecules such as miRNAs, piRNAs, snRNAs, snoRNAs, circRNAs and tRNA in buffalo milk somatic cells and is a step towards complete annotation of the buffalo genome.

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